

Experiences of LGBTQ+ Employees, Job-Seekers and Workplace Dynamics in North East Indian Cities

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Abstract: This study examines workplace experiences of LGBTQ+ employees in North Eastern India with a focus on discrimination and acceptance in urban centres like Guwahati and Shillong after decriminalisation of homosexuality in 2018. Despite progress, significant challenges persist that worsen the economic prospects of LGBTQ+ employees and job candidates. Snowball sampling was used to conduct semi-structured interviews with a total of 32 LGBTQ+ individuals along with five Human Resource (HR) officials and eight coworkers. Thematic analysis revealed several key patterns regarding workplace discrimination and culture. These participants reported overt biases in hiring, microaggressions, workplace ostracism, which have consequently caused mental health challenges and feelings of isolation. Some HR representatives were supportive of inclusivity, but the systemic biases were strong and thus organisational change is necessary to encourage job opportunities based on equity. The results highlight that organisations should implement policies of inclusivity, provide mental health support, and work to create a respectful environment that can enhance well-being among LGBTQ+ individuals and advance their careers. Future research should evaluate the long-term effects of discrimination and the effectiveness of inclusivity interventions.

Keywords: LGBTQ+, North East India, Workplace, Discrimination, Microaggression, Ostracism.

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The year 2018 was a milestone for the LGBTQ+ rights when Section 377 was abolished. This decriminalisation of homosexuality in India was seen as a step towards greater social inclusion of the LGBTQ+ community (Kaur, 2024). Following this legal reform, many workplaces began adopting diversity initiatives, aiming to create environments where LGBTQ+ individuals could feel accepted and valued. Despite these efforts, LGBTQ+ employees and job-seekers in India continued to experience discrimination, particularly in hiring practices, promotion pathways and salary equity, which undermined their economic prospects and reinforced existing social stigmas (Aaberg, 2024). North East India, with its distinctive cultural landscape, offers a unique context for these experiences. While some cities in the region have shown signs of progressive acceptance through local pride events and advocacy, traditional attitudes often restrict genuine inclusion, leading to varied experiences for LGBTQ+ individuals entering the workforce.

Of late, major urban centres such as Guwahati, Dibrugarh and Shillong have seen emergence of pride movements which have sparked dialogue and public awareness regarding the LGBTQ+ issues. However, whether or not these developments have eliminated the subtle and overt discrimination that LGBTQ+ employees face is yet to be studied. This study examines these challenges by focusing on the perspectives of LGBTQ+ employees and job-seekers, as well as their counterparts—HR professionals and co-workers—within urban centres of North East India. Through interviews with these stakeholders, the study seeks to reveal the experiences of the LGBTQ+ community in their professional lives in the emerging cities of North East India. By focusing on the disparities, this study seeks to contribute to an understanding of the gaps in workplace inclusivity and highlight the continued need for reform in both policy and practice.

Literature Review

LGBTQ+ individuals face extensive and persistent discrimination in workplace settings, impacting their professional experiences and overall well-being (Maji et al., 2024; Mara et al., 2021). Research has identified various manifestations of workplace discrimination, including wage penalties (Mize, 2016), biased hiring practices (Baert, 2018; Kattari et al., 2016; Ng et al., 2012), bullying (Hoel et al., 2021; Lacatena et al., 2024), heterosexist harassment (Adikaram & Liyanage, 2021; Lacatena et al., 2024), microaggressions (Smith & Griffiths, 2022) and attacks on dignity (D’Cruz et al., 2021). Workplace discrimination against LGBTQ+ employees often falls into two categories: microaggressions and social ostracism. A microaggression is a subtle, sometimes

even unconsciously committed, act of bias or discrimination. Microaggressions are routine, everyday interactions or statements that at first glance can sound innocent but have a damaging and offensive impact on certain groups of persons, most particularly, marginalized groups. Microaggressions at workplace involve heterosexist or transphobic language, endorsement of heteronormative norms, and explicit or implicit disapproval of LGBTQ+ identities (Maji & Sarika, 2024). Social ostracism is the deliberate exclusion or rejection of an individual or group from a social environment or community. It involves isolating someone by denying them participation in social activities, conversations, or group dynamics. Social ostracism at the workplace encompasses the exclusion of LGBTQ+ individuals from workplace networks and mainstream social groups, creating a climate of isolation and non-inclusivity (Peng & Salter, 2021).

Discrimination occurs at multiple levels within organizations. At the overt level, LGBTQ+ individuals frequently face wage penalties (Mize, 2016), tenure denials (Eliason, 2024), and delayed promotions (Eliason et al., 2018). Hiring discrimination, one of the most common forms of bias, results in LGBTQ+ applicants receiving fewer callbacks compared to their heterosexual peers (Bryant-Lees & Kite, 2021; Weichselbaumer, 2020). Traditional beliefs about gender roles and sexual orientation held by hiring professionals contribute to these biased evaluations, thus disadvantaging LGBTQ+ applicants in the hiring process (Bryant-Lees & Kite, 2021; Mize & Manago, 2018). Interestingly, studies have shown that internet-based hiring, which lacks face-to-face interaction, significantly reduces discriminatory hiring biases against LGBTQ+ applicants (Flage, 2020).

Distal or structural forms of discrimination are more covert, occurring within organizational systems, policies, and practices that inadvertently perpetuate inequality (Dipboye & Colella, 2013). Subtle discrimination can be embedded within organizational structures, leading to barriers that, although not overt, restrict LGBTQ+ employees' advancement and inclusivity (DeSouza et al., 2017). This structural discrimination emphasizes the need for workplaces to evaluate and modify organizational systems and policies to promote genuine inclusivity and reduce the institutional biases that affect LGBTQ+ employees.

Methodology

Study Area

The capital cities of Guwahati and Shillong in Assam and Meghalaya respectively were taken as the study area. In North East India, Guwahati and Shillong are the largest urban centres, which are conducive for studying the

challenges faced by the LGBTQ+ in the workplace due to their diverse job markets and growing corporate presence. The matrilineal culture of Shillong provides a backdrop that is relatively more open but still dominated by traditional ethos. Guwahati, being one of the fast-modernizing cities, represents a mix of traditional and urban diverse values. Both are centres for the activism of LGBTQ+ people, with active support groups operating in these towns and community initiatives being carried out, which forms a very relevant background to comprehend social acceptance and workplace inclusion.

Sampling

This study utilised a snowball sampling method to recruit participants, beginning with a select group of initial participants who identified as LGBTQ+. The initial participants were recruited from local community centres and LGBTQ+ organisations in Guwahati and Shillong. These participants were encouraged to refer others within their networks who identified as LGBTQ+ and were either currently employed or actively seeking employment. This approach facilitated the recruitment of a diverse range of participants, ensuring representation from various socio-economic backgrounds and sectors.

In addition to LGBTQ+ employees and job seekers, the sample included five HR officials responsible for recruitment and workplace policies, and eight coworkers who worked alongside LGBTQ+ employees. This comprehensive sampling strategy aimed to include multiple perspectives on workplace dynamics, discrimination, and acceptance, providing a richer understanding of the experiences of LGBTQ+ individuals in the workplace.

Table 1. City-wise breakdown of Respondents.

	Guwahati	Shillong	Total
LGBTQ+ Employees	11	10	21
LGBTQ+ Job Seekers	6	5	11
Gay	5	4	09
Lesbian	5	4	09
Transgender Female	3	3	06
Transgender Male	2	3	05
Non-Binary	1	1	02
HR Officials	3	2	04
Coworkers of LGBTQ+ Employees	4	4	08

The final sample (see Table 1) comprised 21 LGBTQ+ employees, 11 LGBTQ+ job seekers, 5 human resources (HR) officials and 8 coworkers of LGBTQ+ employees. Of the total 32 LGBTQ+ participants, 10 were gay males, 9 lesbian females, 7 transgender female, 5 transgender male and 1 non-binary person. The participants worked or sought work across different industries (see Table 2). All participants were required to be over 18 years of age, working in Guwahati or Shillong and willing to share their experiences related to workplace dynamics, discrimination and acceptance.

Table 2. Job Category of Respondents

	Sector			
	Corporate	Education	Healthcare	Hospitality
LGBTQ+ Employees	7	4	5	5
LGBTQ+ Job Seekers	4	2	3	2
HR Officials	2	1	1	1
Coworkers	3	1	2	2

Source: Field Survey

Data Collection

Semi-structured interviews were employed as the primary method of data collection. An interview guide was developed to provide flexibility while exploring participants' experiences. The guide was pilot-tested with two participants to ensure clarity and relevance of the questions. Key areas covered in the interviews included:

- Experiences of hiring discrimination and biases in recruitment processes.
- Instances of workplace discrimination, including microaggressions and bullying.
- Perceptions of acceptance and support from coworkers and supervisors.
- HR policies and practices related to diversity and inclusion.
- Attitudes and perspectives of HR officials and coworkers regarding hiring and working with LGBTQ+ individuals.
- Overall workplace culture and environment for LGBTQ+ individuals.

Interviews were conducted either in-person at a neutral location or via secure online platforms, depending on participant preference. Each interview lasted between 30 to 60 minutes and was audio-recorded with participants' consent. To ensure the accuracy of the data, interviews were transcribed verbatim, maintaining confidentiality by assigning pseudonyms to participants. The data was collected between September-November 2023. The iterative nature of the interviews allowed emerging themes from early discussions to inform subsequent interviews, facilitating a deeper exploration of relevant topics. Sampling continued until thematic saturation was reached, indicating that no new themes were emerging from the data.

Analysis and Interpretation

Thematic analysis, following Braun & Clarke's (2006) six-step approach, was utilized to analyse the interview data. The initial step involved immersing the researcher in the data by reading and re-reading the transcripts, which provided a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences. Initial notes and reflections were recorded to highlight significant patterns related to workplace discrimination and acceptance.

Data analysis was conducted through line-by-line coding of the transcripts. Categories were developed using an open-coding technique, capturing various aspects of LGBTQ+ experiences in the workplace, such as "hiring discrimination," "microaggressions," "support from colleagues," "HR perspectives on diversity," and "coworker attitudes." This included both theoretical concepts and data-driven themes arising from the interviews. As the initial codes were generated, the researcher proceeded to the theme development phase, grouping related codes into potential themes and sub-themes. Major themes emerged as central topics. Each theme was reviewed for coherence and consistency within itself and in relation to the overall dataset, ensuring alignment with the study's objectives.

The final analysis phase involved refining themes and sub-themes to accurately represent the data. The researcher reviewed the coded data, collapsing, separating, or reinterpreting themes as necessary. This iterative process ensured a comprehensive analysis reflecting the diverse experiences of participants.

Collaborative discussions with research team members also played a vital role in validating the findings. Feedback from the team provided an opportunity for the researcher to refine the coding frame and thematic structure, ensuring the analysis was grounded in the participants' experiences. Thematic analysis thus formed the basis for an in-depth discussion on workplace discrimination, acceptance, and the broader social implications for LGBTQ+

individuals in North East India, including insights from HR officials and coworkers regarding their views on hiring and collaborating with LGBTQ+ individuals in the workplace.

Results

Experiences of Hiring Discrimination

The experiences of hiring discrimination emerged as a central theme in understanding the challenges faced by LGBTQ+ job seekers in North East Indian cities. Despite the abolishment of Article 377 and a growing recognition of LGBTQ+ rights, pervasive discrimination during the hiring process continues to hinder equal employment opportunities for this community. The interviews revealed various dimensions of discrimination, ranging from overt biases to subtle microaggressions, affecting the job search experiences and mental well-being of LGBTQ+ individuals.

Overt Discrimination

Many LGBTQ+ job seekers recounted experiences of overt discrimination, where their sexual orientation or gender identity led to immediate rejection during the hiring process. Participants shared stories of being told directly that they would not be considered for a position due to their identity.

A 31-year-old Gay male, job seeker shared his experience-

I remember going for an interview at a well-known tech company. The hiring manager was friendly at first, but as soon as I mentioned that I was openly gay, his demeanour changed completely. He started asking me questions about my personal life, and I could sense he was uncomfortable. When I asked about the company's culture, he said, 'We prefer someone more... traditional.' It felt like a slap in the face. I left the interview feeling dejected and wondering if I would ever find a place where I could truly be myself.

Such blatant expressions of bias not only resulted in lost job opportunities but also left lasting scars on the individuals' self-esteem and confidence. This type of discrimination reinforces a negative narrative surrounding LGBTQ+ identities in the workplace, leading individuals to internalize feelings of inferiority.

Subtle Bias and Microaggressions

In addition to overt discrimination, many participants described experiences characterized by subtle biases and microaggressions. These included remarks that, while not explicitly discriminatory, conveyed a lack of acceptance

or understanding of LGBTQ+ identities. For instance, several interviewees mentioned feeling uneasy during interviews when questions about personal lives seemed to probe for their sexual orientation.

A 24-year-old transgender female shared her experience-

I went to an interview at a marketing agency, and the interviewer kept referring to me by my old name, even after I corrected them. It was awkward, and I could tell they were trying to be polite, but it felt dismissive. Then they asked me about my plans for the future, implying that I might not fit in with their 'team culture.' It wasn't direct discrimination, but the undertone was clear—they were judging me not just on my qualifications but on my identity. It made me question whether I could ever be accepted for who I am in a workplace.

Such experiences highlighted the discomfort that LGBTQ+ individuals face when navigating traditional hiring practices that do not account for diverse identities.

Fear of Disclosure

The fear of disclosing one's LGBTQ+ identity became a recurrent theme throughout the interviews. Many job seekers expressed anxiety about revealing their sexual orientation or gender identity, fearing it would jeopardize their chances of being hired.

A 28-year-old lesbian female mentioned-

When I was getting ready for my interview at a tech company, I felt this knot in my stomach. I liked the role, but I couldn't stop thinking about how they might react if I mentioned my girlfriend. I'd heard people say that the company had a conservative vibe, and I worried I'd be judged more for who I am than for my skills. During the interview, when they asked about how I work in a team, I hesitated. Should I be open about my life, or just play it safe? I decided to hold back; it felt easier that way. But honestly, it sucked to feel like I had to hide such a big part of myself.

This apprehension not only impacts their authenticity but also limits their ability to advocate for inclusive workplace environments.

Impact on Mental Health and Job Searching

The emotional toll of experiencing discrimination during the hiring process was profound. Participants reported feelings of anxiety, depression, and low self-worth resulting from repeated rejections and biased treatment.

A 25-year-old gay male, now employed, shared:

Every rejection I faced took a toll on my mental health. After a series of interviews where I felt I was not considered because of my identity, I began to doubt my worth. I started experiencing anxiety before interviews, thinking, 'What if they judge me again?' It got to the point where I almost stopped applying for jobs altogether. The pressure to conform to their expectations was overwhelming, and it affected my self-esteem. It felt like a constant battle between who I am and who I need to be to get hired.

The constant struggle against discrimination significantly affects job seekers' mental health, which in turn influences their motivation and resilience in pursuing employment opportunities. This highlights the need for organizations to recognize and address the psychological impacts of hiring discrimination on LGBTQ+ individuals.

Experiences of Workplace Discrimination

This theme examines the multifaceted experiences of discrimination LGBTQ+ individuals face within their workplaces, including bullying, microaggressions, and the effects of limited management support. The data reveal patterns that show how such discrimination affects job satisfaction, mental well-being, and professional growth, with individuals responding through varied coping mechanisms to manage these challenges.

Ostracism and Social Exclusion

Ostracism and subtle exclusion from informal networks and daily social activities emerged as a common thread. LGBTQ+ employees described how they were often left out of casual gatherings or excluded from essential conversations, affecting both their sense of belonging and career prospects.

For instance, a 34-year-old employee, who identifies as non-binary, shared a particularly impactful experience-

There was this ongoing joke in my team — every time they'd talk about weekend plans, I was left out. I'd walk by and hear my name mentioned, but when I'd join in, it would go silent. Eventually, I stopped trying to join these conversations. It felt like a high school clique, and it hurt more than I thought it would. One time, I overheard my manager tell a colleague that my 'vibe was off' for the team. That moment broke my confidence completely, and I began questioning every little thing I did or said around them.

This ongoing ostracism not only affected their confidence but also fostered a sense of isolation that carried into their professional life, where opportunities for collaboration and mentorship became increasingly out of reach.

Microaggressions and Stereotyped Comments

Microaggressions often manifested as seemingly innocent but deeply offensive remarks and jokes that reinforced stereotypes or undermined participants' capabilities. These statements, often framed as friendly banter, left participants feeling marginalized and pigeonholed.

A 26-year-old employee, gay male, shared a recurring experience-

People in my department seem to assume I'd naturally be good at things like decorating or organizing team parties — 'the fun stuff,' they call it. My boss would say, 'Why don't you add some flair to this presentation?' at almost every team meeting. I felt like no one saw me as a serious professional, just as the 'creative gay guy.' I tried speaking up once, saying I was interested in a more analytical project, but my supervisor laughed it off, saying I should 'stick to what I'm good at.' Over time, I found myself shrinking back, almost pretending to like what they assumed about me just to avoid conflict.

This type of microaggression contributed to feelings of frustration and invisibility, as LGBTQ+ employees felt stereotyped, rather than valued, for their professional contributions.

Criticism of Appearance and Demeanor

Comments about appearance were particularly challenging for transgender employees, who often found themselves subjected to scrutiny based on how they presented themselves.

A 24-year-old employee, transgender male, recounted an experience that highlighted the tension between his professional identity and his authentic gender expression-

My manager pulled me aside after a meeting and said, 'You know, you might want to look a bit more... polished. Maybe tone down some of the masculine things, like the short hair and the clothes.' I could tell he was trying to be 'helpful,' but it felt like he was saying, 'You're too trans for this job.' I started to dread mornings, overthinking every outfit, wondering if my clothes would be 'professional' enough. Eventually, I felt like I was wearing a mask every day — but that mask also drained my energy and authenticity. I'm still figuring out how to navigate that line, but every comment chips away at my confidence.

The recurring focus on conforming to traditional norms of appearance created a constant psychological burden for LGBTQ+ employees, often forcing them to suppress or alter their self-expression.

Limited Management Support and Lack of Accountability

The absence of adequate HR support was a recurring issue for many participants, who found their concerns dismissed or downplayed.

In one notable case, A 25-year-old, transgender female shared her frustration with HR's response to repeated incidents of misgendering-

After six months of correcting people, I thought I'd ask HR for help. I explained how painful it was each time I was misgendered, especially in front of clients. But the HR manager just nodded and said, 'People need time to adjust.' Weeks passed, and nothing changed. They didn't even bring it up in team meetings. I started to feel like I was just a problem they wanted to sweep under the rug. It made me question if staying was worth it, if every day would be another battle just to be acknowledged.

This lack of HR intervention not only signalled insufficient support for LGBTQ+ employees but also reinforced a broader organizational culture that deprioritized inclusivity and accountability.

Psychological Toll on Job Performance and Well-being

The psychological strain resulting from these experiences impacted job performance and well-being, as LGBTQ+ employees grappled with the emotional burden of discrimination.

A 28-year-old lesbian female articulated this effect poignantly-

It's exhausting. I'm constantly in a state of vigilance, questioning if people are judging me for who I am. Every time there's a promotion opportunity, I hesitate to apply because I wonder if they'd take me seriously. It's almost like a slow burn — the stress builds up until I find myself avoiding tasks, delaying deadlines, just trying to shield myself from one more moment of doubt or discomfort. I'm starting to question if this job is even worth it, if it's possible to thrive here.

For many, the constant emotional toll created a cycle of anxiety, hindering their ability to fully engage and excel in their roles, thereby limiting career growth and satisfaction.

Limited Mentorship and Sponsorship Opportunities

LGBTQ+ employees also highlighted a lack of mentors and sponsors who could support their career progression. The absence of role models within the company, especially those who identified as LGBTQ+, left many participants feeling unsupported and isolated in their careers.

A 22-year-old employee, a gay male, expressed the difficulties of navigating the workplace without mentorship-

Everyone around me seems to have a mentor or a senior person rooting for them, pulling them into new projects or advising them on how to move up. But I don't have that, and I'm not sure why. Maybe they're uncomfortable with me, or maybe they think I'm not 'serious' enough. I feel like I'm missing out on opportunities to grow, simply because there's no one in my corner.

For him, the lack of mentorship contributed to a sense of being stalled professionally, as he observed others advancing with the support and guidance of senior leaders while he navigated career obstacles alone.

Glass Ceiling for LGBTQ+ Employees

Participants consistently reported feeling they were facing an unspoken "glass ceiling" within the organization, where their potential for advancement seemed capped. Many LGBTQ+ employees described experiences where promotions were subtly implied to be out of reach unless they conformed to certain expectations.

A 32-year-old employee, transgender female, shared her struggle with perceived limitations-

I've been in this role for over five years, while newer hires with less experience have moved up. I was subtly told once by a senior colleague that people 'aren't ready for such a radical change in leadership style,' and I knew what he meant. It feels like my potential stops at my current position, regardless of my skills. Each promotion that passes me by feels like confirmation that I'm seen as different in a way that's limiting, not empowering.

This experience illustrates the challenge of the "glass ceiling" for LGBTQ+ employees, where their identities were subtly referenced as incompatible with higher leadership roles, suggesting a persistent and systemic bias within organizational culture.

Resilience and Peer Support Networks

In response to these challenges, LGBTQ+ employees found solace and strength in informal peer networks, often forming close bonds with others who had similar experiences.

A 30-year-old employee, a bisexual female, shared how these networks provided a lifeline:

After one rough week, I connected with another queer colleague, and we just vented. It felt like a weight was lifted, just knowing I wasn't alone. Over time, a small group of us began meeting for coffee or lunch — it became our safe space, where we didn't have to hide who we were. These little moments helped me recharge and face each day. It's strange, but without these friends, I might not still be here.

These informal support networks highlighted the power of shared experiences and camaraderie in sustaining resilience, underscoring how connection with others could offset the isolation often experienced in the workplace.

HR and Coworkers' Perspectives on LGBTQ+ Inclusion

This theme examines the attitudes of HR professionals and coworkers towards LGBTQ+ inclusion in the workplace. Despite increasing diversity and inclusion initiatives, biases and systemic challenges persist. For some, the presence of LGBTQ+ employees remains controversial, influenced by personal discomfort and entrenched societal norms.

Reluctance to Recruit LGBTQ+ Employees

Some HR officials, while advocating for inclusion on paper, conveyed hesitation about recruiting openly LGBTQ+ individuals due to anticipated discomfort among existing employees. Several HR professionals expressed that while they strive for diversity, they also have to manage perceived “tensions” that could arise in the workplace.

One HR participant explained the challenge of balancing inclusivity with workplace harmony-

We're committed to inclusivity, but when it comes to hiring LGBTQ+ individuals, we have to think practically. Sometimes, it's not about our policies but the reactions we see from others. If people are uncomfortable, it creates an awkward environment. Unfortunately, that factors into our hiring decisions.

This reluctance reflects a challenge in implementation, where the fear of disrupting the ‘comfort’ of non-LGBTQ+ employees can hinder equal opportunity in hiring.

Another HR participant noted the subtle but significant influence of client preferences on hiring decisions, particularly in public-facing roles-

There are cases where we have to consider client reactions as well, especially in positions where an LGBTQ+ employee would interact with customers frequently. It's unfortunate, but sometimes it impacts our decision-making.

These perspectives illustrate how implicit biases can manifest in recruitment practices, as HR departments struggle to reconcile corporate inclusivity with anticipated social discomfort.

Coworkers' Discomfort and Perceptions of 'Norms'

Among some coworkers, the inclusion of LGBTQ+ colleagues evoked discomfort rooted in prevailing cultural and social norms. LGBTQ+ employees were sometimes perceived as "different" or "against the norm," which affected the workplace dynamics. Such perceptions often led to subtle ostracism, where coworkers avoided collaboration or maintained a social distance from LGBTQ+ colleagues.

A coworker shared their discomfort candidly-

It's not easy working alongside someone who doesn't fit into our usual environment. It just feels different, like they don't belong in the same way. Maybe it's because we're not used to it, or it goes against what we're comfortable with.

Another coworker reflected on the clash with traditional norms-

People here have strong views about how people should behave and present themselves. So, seeing someone dress or act in a way that's not typical creates tension, even if it's not said out loud. It's like they're challenging the 'right way' of doing things.

This subtheme highlights that, while LGBTQ+ employees may not face overt hostility, discomfort stemming from ingrained norms subtly reinforces exclusion.

Microaggressions and Stereotypical Comments

Microaggressions emerged as a recurring challenge for LGBTQ+ employees, where coworkers made subtle comments on their appearance, demeanour, or perceived "fit" for certain roles. These comments, while often downplayed as harmless, perpetuated stereotypes and contributed to an environment of continuous scrutiny for LGBTQ+ individuals.

A coworker shared an example of how an LGBTQ+ colleague's appearance was frequently the topic of comments-

Whenever our LGBTQ+ teammate wears something more colourful or stands out, someone always has to say something like, 'Wow, you're dressed

to impress today,' or 'That's a bold look.' They might think it's funny, but you can tell it's not supportive.

Another HR official noted the fine line between “jokes” and discrimination:

In meetings, you hear side comments, even jokes that aren't explicitly offensive but are directed at LGBTQ+ employees. They might seem minor, but they add up, making it feel like these employees are always being singled out.

These microaggressions reinforce the need for deeper, ongoing awareness efforts within organizations to address biases that can marginalize LGBTQ+ employees.

Discussion

The findings from this study highlight the pervasive nature of hiring discrimination faced by LGBTQ+ individuals in North East Indian cities. Despite legal advancements, such as the decriminalization of homosexuality through the abolishment of Article 377, societal attitudes and workplace cultures continue to foster an environment where discrimination, both overt and subtle, is prevalent. This discussion elaborates on the implications of these findings, emphasizing the need for organizational accountability, the psychological impact on LGBTQ+ individuals, and the necessity for robust support systems within workplaces.

Experiences of LGBTQ+ in Guwahati and Shillong- Different or Similar?

Despite differences in size, demography, and societal contexts, the experiences that LGBTQ+ individuals have gone through in Guwahati and Shillong barely have much difference. In both cities, conservative attitudes toward LGBTQ+ individuals, coupled with limited public understanding of LGBTQ+ identities, sustain stigma by society. While Guwahati offers a little more visibility with a larger community of people with LGBTQ+ orientation and some formal support networks, in Shillong, which is much smaller in size, grassroots efforts and informal networks also show up. In both cities, LGBTQ+ people live their lives in an atmosphere of acceptance, which is mostly confined to private spaces or close-knit groups, with very few places in the public sphere to express themselves freely. The experience, in total, is generally the same: social pressures, the search for spaces, and limited visibility to overcome.

Hiring & Workplace Discrimination

Consistent to earlier research by Bryant-Lees & Kite (2021) and Weichselbaumer (2020), the experiences of overt discrimination recounted by

participants reveal a harsh reality: LGBTQ+ job seekers often encounter blatant biases that result in immediate rejection. This not only affects their chances of securing employment but also has detrimental effects on their self-esteem and overall mental health. The narratives shared by participants underscore a troubling cycle where the rejection based on identity perpetuates a narrative of inferiority. Such experiences call for organizations to implement training programs aimed at addressing unconscious biases among hiring managers and to promote inclusivity in recruitment practices (Bryant-Lees & Kite, 2021).

Moreover, the subtle biases and microaggressions that many participants faced indicate a deeper, systemic issue within organizational cultures. This is consistent with previous research findings by Sadika et al. (2020) and Smith & Griffiths (2022). These forms of discrimination may not always be overtly damaging, but they contribute to an environment that undermines the dignity and identity of LGBTQ+ individuals. The discomfort expressed by LGBTQ+ employees during interviews, often stemming from probing questions about their personal lives, highlights the urgent need for companies to adopt inclusive hiring practices that respect and affirm diverse identities. The experiences of workplace discrimination, characterized by ostracism, microaggressions, and limited support from management, further illuminate the systemic barriers faced by LGBTQ+ employees. These narratives reflect a concerning culture of exclusion that not only affects job satisfaction but also stifles professional growth. The reported instances of being overlooked for social engagements and informal networks highlight the social isolation LGBTQ+ employees often experience. This exclusion is detrimental not only to individual well-being but also to team cohesion and overall organizational culture.

Moreover, the impact of microaggressions on the workplace dynamics reveals how entrenched biases can manifest in subtle, yet damaging ways. Participants' experiences of being stereotyped based on their sexual orientation or gender identity demonstrate the need for training programs focused on fostering empathy and understanding among employees. Organizations must prioritize creating an environment where all employees feel valued for their contributions, rather than reduced to stereotypes.

Organizations should consider revising their interview protocols to minimize discomfort and ensure that all candidates feel respected and valued for their qualifications rather than judged based on their identity. The lack of mentorship and support systems for LGBTQ+ employees, as highlighted in the findings, further exacerbates the challenges they face. Mentorship plays a crucial role in professional development, and the absence of supportive figures can hinder career progression (Webster & Adams, 2023). Organizations should

actively implement mentorship programs that connect LGBTQ+ employees with allies and advocates within the workplace to facilitate their growth and success.

Psychological Impact

Consistent with earlier research (Owens et al., 2022; Thuillier et al., 2022) the psychological toll of discrimination is evident in the mental health struggles reported by participants, including anxiety, depression, and diminished self-worth. These challenges hinder job seekers' motivation and resilience, suggesting a dire need for organizations to recognize and address the psychological impacts of discrimination. The emotional strain described by participants illustrates the profound effects of feeling compelled to hide one's identity in professional settings. To counteract this, organizations should develop mental health support systems and provide resources for LGBTQ+ employees to cope with discrimination (Mara et al., 2021). Additionally, creating safe spaces for dialogue and support within the workplace can help alleviate the psychological burden of navigating discrimination (Mara et al., 2021).

The fear of disclosing one's identity, as expressed by participants, not only restricts authenticity but also stifles the potential for fostering inclusive environments. This apprehension indicates a broader societal stigma that continues to affect the workplace dynamics. Encouraging openness and inclusivity through policy changes, coupled with awareness campaigns about the importance of diversity, can help diminish the fear of disclosure and promote a healthier work environment for LGBTQ+ individuals (Thuillier et al., 2022).

Conclusion and Future Directions

This study sheds light on the still ongoing challenges faced by the LGBTQ+ employees and job seekers in the cities of North East India despite the recent legal progress in the LGBTQ+ rights movement. The discrimination manifests in various forms such as biases while hiring, microaggression at the workplace, social ostracism and limited support from the management. While some HR officials and coworkers expressed that the environment is gradually becoming inclusive, there still exists systemic bias which continues to hinder meaningful change. When compared to the rest of Indian cities like Mumbai, Delhi or Bangalore, the corporate diversity initiatives are less visible in the North East Indian cities. Cities of North East India are still lacking in widespread formal inclusion policies, or if it is in place, still haven't been able to operationalise their administration. This has made job opportunities, job security and career growth more precarious for LGBTQ+ employees and job seekers.

An interesting aspect that emerged during the interviews, which was not explicitly addressed but was implicitly implied, was the phenomenon of *passing*. Passing is the phenomenon where LGBTQ+ individuals try to conceal their gender identity to avoid discrimination. Several participants described the pressure to change their mannerisms, way they dress or speak to adhere with heteronormative workplace environments. Although it offers temporary respite from the biases, over time it takes a psychological toll on individuals since they have to suppress their original selves. Future research should further investigate the role of passing, how it is employed as a workplace survival strategy and its impact on long-term career progression, as well as its adverse psychological impact.

To establish a truly inclusive workplace, organisations must go beyond diversity efforts, which are just symbolic and implement substantive changes in inclusive policies. This could be done by adopting a bias-free recruitment (such as having one LGBTQ+ member in the selection committee), enforcing anti-discrimination policies, as well as providing mental health support, which is tailored for LGBTQ+ employees. Further, sensitisation training and seminars can help create awareness and foster acceptance among the coworkers towards their LGBTQ+ colleagues. Additionally, creating mentorship programs and safe spaces for LGBTQ+ professionals can help mitigate isolation and enhance career advancement.

Ultimately, this study underscores the urgent need for a cultural shift in organizational structures. By actively addressing biases and fostering a work environment based on equity and respect, workplaces in North East India can move towards genuine inclusion, benefiting not only LGBTQ+ employees but the broader workforce as well.

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